

GAME IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPEECH AND FORMATION OF CREATIVE THINKING IN CHILDREN

Tadjibaeva Adila Ergashevna

The Fergana Branch of Tashkent University of
Information Technology,
Senior Teacher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10008171>

Abstract: The correct and effective use of game activities in the preschool educational organization increases the effectiveness of each training and field trip. In pre-school educational institutions, game activities are conducted in various forms, eventful - performing, action, educational, musical-educational. In order for the game to be interesting and meaningful for children, the educator should be familiar with the rules of the game.

Key words: game, development, speech, formation, creative thinking.

Children's thinking expands and their interests develop through action-packed games. Through role-playing games, children get to know the daily life of the people around them, their relationships, and their ways of getting married..

From fairy tales suitable for children's age, staging Russian folk tales "Turnip", "Bo`girsok", Uzbek folk tales "Emerald and expensive", "Two goats", remember songs, poems, jokes. drawing trains the child's memory, helps to develop abilities such as the ability to gather thoughts, vocabulary, speech activity, aesthetic culture, performing skills, self-confidence in children.

Through educational games, the child's ability to consciously approach the issue of independence, activity, and creativity grows. The game is conducted through demonstration, simple to complex methods. During the educational games, the educator activates the child's movement, forms the ability to act independently, if the game is used correctly, the child's thinking, speech, memory, that is, the mental education of the child is founded. Through educational games, children learn the properties of various things and the materials used in making them, compare them with each other, and divide them into groups through the organs of hearing, sight, and feeling. Educational games are held in small groups as follows.

1. Games with toys - "What do bears need?", "Our little feet", "Dresses for Emerald".
2. Games that can be played on the table - "What goes where?", "Show me what I said", "Who has what in his hand?".
3. Oral educational games - "Let's bathe the doll Lola Khan", "The doll Lola

Khan came to visit", "Amazing bag", "Find the shape", "Find the color" games like

To activate the organs of hearing and sight, "Find the bark", "What tree is the fruit?", "Find the fruit", "Fruits and leaves", "Domino", "Wild and domestic animals", "What is needed to work", "What animal lives in this house", "Who or what is this?" it is appropriate to use such games. Through these games, children's imaginations such as fruits and vegetables, animals and birds, seasons, clothes, etc., are enriched and expanded, and the features of seeing and hearing and remembering are developed. The spirit of love for work is cultivated through the games "Aiting biz topamiz", "Topgan topagon", "Ashkovoq pishdi", "Mud game", "Gardeners" played in large groups.

The role of musical-educational games in increasing children's love for music is incomparable. By showing and playing various musical instruments, the teacher introduces the sound, structure and types of musical instruments. Through games such as "Find from the sound", "What am I playing", "How is the bell ringing", the educator teaches children to distinguish the sound characteristics of voices and musical instruments. Through national games such as "Tapur-tupur kairagoch", "I threw a stone at the roof", "Play", "Sanamar", "Fists and palms", "Yomgir" children move to the rhythm of music. They will be taught how to sing, clap and mimic movements correctly.- Geese, will you say a word?

- ra, ra - ra!
- Do you eat oatmeal?
- Yes, yes - yes
- Why are you stroking the feather?
- gok, gok - gok.
- What do you want from me?
- Look, look, look"!

Such poems teach children to develop their speech, to think independently, to draw conclusions from life's impressions.

Therefore, pedagogues should pay attention to the following requirements when organizing children's games that provide knowledge or strengthen their knowledge for preschool children:

- the content of the game should be educational and educational;
- the images about the reflected things should be correct and complete,
- game actions should be actively aimed at a certain goal and have a creative nature.

Also, it is necessary to lead the game, taking into account the interests of

all and some children, to use toys and necessary materials appropriately, and to ensure that children are happy and benevolent in the game.

In short, the pedagogue, while leading children's play, affects all aspects of the child's personality: mind, emotions, will, behavior, and from this, children are mentally, morally, aesthetically and physically, as well as economically educated. should be used. Then, as a result of games, children's knowledge and imagination will be enriched and deepened.

References:

1. Kuzibaevna, O. G. (2020). Technologies of developing the ecological culture of students in the process of learning a foreign languages in higher educational institutions. *Solid State Technology*, 63(1s), 1816-1825.
2. Kuzibaevna, O. G. (2021). Analysis of Effective Ways to Develop Students' Environmental Culture in Foreign Language Teaching. *Central asian journal of literature, philosophy and culture*, 2(12), 37-43.
3. Обидова, Г. (2021). Развитие экологической культуры в образовательных моделях развитых стран мира. *Общество и инновации*, 2(10/S), 251-256.
4. Tadjibaeva, A., & Tashlanova, N. (2020). The collaborative approach in content and language learning. *Теория и практика современной науки*, (6 (60)), 31-34.
5. Mamatovich, Z. R., & Ergashevna, T. A. (2019). Blended learning in higher education using LMS Moodle. *Образовательный процесс*, (5 (16)), 5-9.
6. Ergashevna, T. A. (2020). Specific features of the language in the development of culture. *Проблемы современной науки и образования*, (3 (148)), 82-84.
7. Mukhammad, K. K., & oqli Melikuziev, A. L. (2022, December). THE ESSENCE OF NONVERBAL COMMUNICATION. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES (Vol. 1, No. 19, pp. 91-93)*.
8. oqli Melikuziev, A. L. (2022). HISTORICAL AND MODERN CLASSIFICATION OF PARALINGUISTICS. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3 (10), 126-128.
9. Sarvinoz, T., & Shodiya, I. (2022). TILSHUNOSLIKDA KOGNITIV LINGVISTIKA SHAKLLANISH TARIXIGA DOIR. *Involta Scientific Journal*, 1(13), 51-54.
10. Ibragimjonovna, A. M. (2023). The Issues Related to Studying of Language and thought in Cognitive Linguistics. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 31, 271-273.
11. Toshpulatova, M., & Ilhomjonova, R. (2023). TEACHING AND LEARNING ENGLISH THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY. *Engineering problems and innovations*.
12. Toshpulatova, M. I. (2022). The main features in teaching English for specific purposes. *Journal of Integrated Education and Research*, 1(5), 207-214.

13. Ikromovna, T. M. (2022). USE OF FOLKTALES IN ENGLISH LESSONS. POLISH SCIENCE JOURNAL, 88.
14. Parpiyeva, M., & Jurayeva, M. (2023). Problems of linguoculturological and neurolinguistic study of phonetic means. American Journal Of Philological Sciences, 3(02), 49-59.
15. Abdug'ofur qizi Jurayeva, M., & SultanovnaUsmanova, S. (2023). Neyrolingvistika sohasini organish tendensiyalari. Involta Scientific Journal, 2(1), 53-59.
16. Abdug'ofur qizi Jurayeva, M., & Alisher o'g'li, M. M. (2023). Morphology and syntax and crosslinguistic findings in neurolinguistics. Образование наука и инновационные идеи в мире, 18(8), 156-159.
17. Dilshoda, R. (2022). THE STRUCTURAL-SEMANTIC FEATURES OF COMPUTER TERMS IN ENGLISH LINGUISTICS. PEDAGOGS jurnali, 20(2), 36-40.
18. Raximjonova, D. (2022). INGLIZ VA O 'ZBEK TILLARIDA KOMPOZITSIYA USULIDA SO 'Z YASALISHI HODISASINING O 'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI. Journal of Integrated Education and Research, 1(4), 710-713.
19. Raximjonova, D. (2023). STRUCTURAL FEATURES OF COMPUTER SOFTWARE TERMS IN ENGLISH LINGUISTICS. Farg 'ona davlat universiteti ilmiy jurnali, (1), 448-452.
20. Djuraevna, T. N. (2023). The Cognitive Aspect of the Purpose of Teaching Foreign Languages. Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices, 16, 88-94.
21. Djuraevna, T. N. (2023). Language Education as A System: Structure, Functions and Main Components. Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities, 14, 141-146.
22. Djurayevna, T. N. (2022). Semantic and structural features of the vocabulary of color designation in english, uzbek and russian languages. Global Book Publishing Services, 01-123.
23. Juraeva, Z. Q. (2017). SPECIFIC FEATURES OF LANGUAGE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CULTURE. Форум молодых ученых, (5 (9)), 5-9.